

Effect of process conditions on *N,N*-dibutylimidazolium chloride recovery by electro dialysis method

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Introduction

Ionic liquids (ILs), due to their unique properties, are applied in many areas of chemistry. One of the ILs, which was successfully used in the dehydration of fructose, cellulose dissolution, and also as a “green” solvent and catalyst at once in Friedlander heteroannulation reaction is *N,N*-dibutylimidazolium chloride ([BBIM]Cl). Unfortunately, its very good miscibility with most solvents caused that, its recovery from wastewater and post-reaction products by conventional separation methods can be inefficient. However, one of the promising methods of the ILs recovery from aqueous solutions is electro dialysis (ED). Therefore the aim of this work was to examine the effect of the [BBIM]Cl concentration, the applied voltage, and the linear flow velocity on the effectiveness of ED in [BBIM]Cl recovery.

Experimental

The [BBIM]Cl recovery was carried out using an EDR-Z/10-0.8 module (MemBrain, Czech Republic) with an effective single membrane area of 64 cm². There were 5 pairs of the heterogeneous Ralex AM(H)-CM(H) membranes (Mega, Czech Republic). The ED module was equipped with a programmable power supply (KORAD KA3010, KORAD Technology co. Ltd, China) and with three tanks named: diluate, concentrate, and electrode rinse solution. All process solutions were recirculated using a peristaltic pump (Masterflex L/S, Cole-Parmer, United States) at a rate corresponding to the linear flow velocity in the range from 1 to 3 cm/s. The ED experiments were conducted at constant voltage (5, 7.5 and 10 V), which was a maximum value determined using the limiting current density test. The concentration of [BBIM]Cl in the diluate and concentrate solutions was in the range from 0.05 to 0.25 mol/L. The ED tests were performed until the diluate conductivity dropped below the 1% of an initial diluate conductivity, which was monitored using a CPC-461 pH/conductivity meter (Elmetron, Poland). The concentrations of [BBIM]Cl in diluate and concentrate solutions were analyzed using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-2700i, Japan). The surface morphology of ion-exchange membranes before and after ED were investigated through the utilization of scanning electron microscopy (FEI Quanta 650 FEG, USA). The performance and effectiveness of electro dialytic [BBIM]Cl recovery were assessed on the basis of the [BBIM]Cl recovery ratio, the [BBIM]Cl concentration degree, the electric current efficiency, as well as energy consumption.

Results and discussion

In this work, the effect of process conditions on the [BBIM]Cl recovery from aqueous solutions by ED was investigated. It was noted that the IL concentration, applied voltage drop, and linear flow velocity had influence on the [BBIM]Cl recovery by ED method. It was found that the [BBIM]Cl recovery and concentration degree increased with increasing [BBIM]Cl concentration in the initial diluate solution. Moreover the highest ED efficiency was obtained when a 2 V electric potential per one membrane pair was applied, using a 2 cm/s linear flow velocity. It was concluded that ED allows for the effective [BBIM]Cl recovery from wastewater by the ED method. The recovery ratio reached above 90%.

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